

Higher Education Institution Faculty Perceptions on Internationalization

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ABSTRACT: Universities prioritize internationalization to prepare students for a globalized world, enhancing their intercultural skills and career opportunities. Faculty involvement is key to internationalization, yet more research is needed on their experiences and professional development. There is a need to investigate more on the engagement barriers, strategic implementation, and faculty engagement towards internationalization. This study aims to understand Higher Education Institutions faculty members' perceptions of internationalization, their awareness, and comprehension of its importance. With the use of descriptive method, the study found that Faculty members broadly support internationalization, but their opinions diverge regarding the adequacy of current institutional support. While they recognize verbal and written encouragement from top leaders, concerns persist about funding for international teaching and research. Suggestions are institutions must strategically align their goals with robust support systems, leveraging faculty diversity and fostering global partnerships to enhance internationalization efforts.

KEYWORDS: Internationalization, HEI Faculty, Support for Internationalization, Challenges for internationalization, Opportunities for internationalization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Internationalization has become a key priority for universities, driven by the need to prepare students for global citizenship and the demands of the globalized workforce (Varghese & Godwin, 2018). Participation in study abroad programs positively impacted students' intercultural competence, global awareness, and career prospects (Stier & Bista, 2020). Internationalization also plays a vital role in research collaboration and knowledge exchange. A report by the International Association of Universities (IAU) (2018) emphasized that international research partnerships and mobility facilitate the sharing of ideas, expertise, and resources, leading to innovative breakthroughs and advancements. The role of faculty in internationalization is crucial, yet there is limited research on their experiences, challenges, and professional development needs in this context (Balicanta, 2018). Further investigation into effective strategies for engaging and supporting faculty in internationalization efforts, including curriculum development, intercultural teaching approaches, and collaborations is essential. The aim of this study is to describe the HEI faculty members' perceptions on internationalization in terms of their awareness and understanding.

Specifically, this study wants to answer the following questions:

1. What are the HEI faculty members' perceptions on internationalization in terms of;
 - 1.1 Institutional support
 - 1.2 Opportunities provided by the institutions
 - 1.3 Challenges
2. Is there a significant difference in the HEI Faculty members perceptions on internationalization when group according to;
 - 2.1 gender
 - 2.2 age
 - 2.3 civil status
 - 2.4 highest degree completed
 - 2.5 years of teaching experience
 - 2.6 courses taught
 - 2.7 type of HEI (Private/Public)
 - 2.8 medium of Instruction
 - 2.9 rank/position (faculty/admin)

- 2.10 International experience in research
- 2.11 International experience in Instruction
- 2.12 Percentage of foreign student
- 2.13 Level of students teaching

1.1 Internationalization in Education

Internationalization can be described as the expansive movement of engaging in global activities to reap specific rewards, which also influences the associated products and actions. Wit and Altbachb (2021) suggests that internationalization is a recent, wide-ranging, and diverse strategy in higher education, influenced by a mix of political, economic, sociocultural, and academic factors and actors. Its effects differ based on the specific circumstances of regions, nations, and institutions. Additionally, Lin (2019) highlights the importance of higher education quality as essential for a nation's economic and social progress. The internationalization of higher education has emerged as a significant movement and policy focus in many developing nations.

In the wave of economic and cultural globalization of the last century, the active push by governments and institutions has transformed internationalization from an ad hoc, marginalized, and decentralized activity to the center of the higher education agenda. This optimism has indeed led to the popular acceptance that internationalization is one of the core drivers of innovation and change in higher education (Wit & Altbachb, 2021). There are several opportunities for international higher education to commit to a Higher Education Social Responsibility Strategy thereby ensuring that the UNESCO 2030 SDGs are collectively achieved through partnership, collaboration, and commitment to enhancing the quality of life of global communities (Patel, 2019). Cooperation and exchanges have always been the mainstream of education internationalization, but in recent years, due to the relatively tense international economic and political situation, the rise of nationalism, and the impact of COVID-19, the competition of school institutions in various countries has intensified. Bondarenko et. al. (2019) emphasize that international educational cooperation is primarily driven by the pursuit of national interests by the involved countries and the growing competitiveness within the global education marketplace.

1.2 Internationalization in HEIs

The expansion of higher education and its pivotal role in the global knowledge economy have led to a surge in the number of international students, making the field more globally competitive, as noted by Wit and Altbachb (2020). Yu (2022) points out that the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted international education and cultural exchanges, leading to a rise in anti-internationalization sentiments within higher education. The pandemic's restrictions have curtailed international mobility, prompting the adoption of new online educational methods. While some pre-pandemic educational trends remain relevant, the pandemic has predominantly had adverse effects, particularly on the economy and students, with schools and nations dependent on international education facing substantial financial challenges. Vindača and Ľubkina (2021) suggest that these existing trends should now incorporate considerations brought about by the pandemic, with a focus on modernization and transformation. Moreover, the current global political

climate and escalating regional conflicts add to the complexities of international education.

Wit and Altbachb (2020) observe that an increasing number of governments worldwide are now focusing on the economic and political aspects, risk management, and ethical implications of international activities conducted by universities. The need to manage export control risks could potentially interfere with global scientific partnerships, especially in vital sectors like health and environmental science. These export controls are likely to affect the movement of students, academics, and educational programs. Concurrently, new players in international education, particularly leading universities from developing nations, are becoming more active participants in the international higher education (IHE) landscape. In 2020, North America held a 22% share of the international student market, while Europe hosted 23%, as reported by the OECD (2020). Ge (2022) notes that Japan and China have risen to the top-10 host countries, with China also being the largest source of international students. A decade earlier, the global financial crisis caught the world off guard, leading to persistent budget cuts in the higher education sector of many wealthy countries.

The growing middle class in emerging countries has fueled a desire for international experience, resulting in increased student mobility. However, we stand at the threshold of another significant transformation. External megatrends, including technological advancements and societal shifts, are poised to drive higher education institutions (especially in high-income countries) toward offering more relevant, affordable, and flexible academic programs (Choudaha & Van, 2018). Despite this trend, the current internationalization of education faces considerable challenges. The COVID-19 pandemic, economic recessions, geopolitical tensions, and the rise of nationalism have complicated cultural exchanges. Additionally, emerging educational institutions and countries are playing a more prominent role, while educational research progresses gradually (Ge, 2022).

1.3 Internationalization in the Philippine HEIs

The Philippines' status as an English-speaking nation provides it with a distinct edge in globalizing its education system. Despite having a shorter duration of basic education compared to other ASEAN countries, the Philippines has consistently

demonstrated high functional literacy rates. This success is partly credited to the enduring impact of diverse foreign cultures, which has cultivated Filipinos' resilience and openness to new concepts, including their proficiency in foreign languages (Alson, 2018). Leveraging these strengths, the Philippines can strategically allocate educational resources to key areas. Current trends in Philippine Higher Education are shifting towards a greater emphasis on global integration, fostering international and regional alliances, and adopting outcome-based competency standards in education (Chao, 2022).

The internationalization of education in the Philippines has been instrumental in advancing the academic offerings of higher education institutions. The clear dedication of institutions, their organizational frameworks, staff, curricula, learning outcomes, faculty practices, student exchanges, and collaborative partnerships have all shown a strong connection to the successful internationalization efforts within Filipino higher education institutions (Narbarte & Chan 2022). Emilson and colleagues (2019) suggest that internationalization relies on factors such as institutional accreditation, infrastructure, policies, and financial planning, recommending that institutions develop strategic plans to tackle these areas. Opportunities for enhancing Philippine Higher Education Institutions' (PHEIs) international presence have been identified through regional and global educational collaborations. PHEIs are engaging in internationalization by participating in study abroad programs, migrant education, and improving their accreditation and rankings (Ramirez, 2019). This process has significantly bolstered the capabilities of Philippine educational institutions by leveraging their unique local strengths.

1.4 Prospects for internationalization

Currently, the emergence of nationalist-populist movements, immigration restrictions, assaults on academic liberties, anti-globalization demonstrations, and Europe's anti-integration sentiment (Brexit) are all factors that could adversely affect the process of internationalization. Wit & Altbachb (2021) argue that it's crucial to concentrate on the significant aspects of internationalization's competitive, exclusive, and market-driven nature. They advocate for a heightened focus on the qualitative facets of internationalization, such as fostering global citizenship, enhancing employability, and improving the caliber of research, education, and social services. Moreover, they recommend shifting the evaluation of internationalization from mere outputs to meaningful outcomes and impacts. Looking ahead, the aim of internationalization in education should be to enhance the quality of educational offerings amidst challenging conditions and intense competition, while broadening the scope to monitor the progression of internationalization trends. In terms of research on internationalization, there's a pronounced emphasis on mobility and research output, yet the processes of internationalization within research receive less attention. This is particularly notable given that addressing today's significant challenges necessitates international collaboration (Rüland & Gräber-Magocsi, 2022).

Given the current global tensions and complexities, a simplistic view is insufficient to foresee the future of educational internationalization. The concept is now intertwined with broader discussions on the knowledge economy, aiming to overcome narrow-mindedness while preparing students for the global job market (Buckner, 2019). The goal of internationalizing education is to meet the needs of all stakeholders, yet today's challenging climate makes this difficult. Ultimately, the direction of educational internationalization will either influence the environment to allow free multilateral interactions or adapt to it, leading to either heightened competition or a trend towards more localized approaches in certain domains.

1.5 Importance of internationalization in HEIs

The primary advantages of internationalization for higher education institutions (HEIs) include the following: improved global collaboration and development of capabilities, expanded international networks among faculty and researchers, and the chance to assess and compare their performance against established international standards (Ferrer, 2020). Internationalization of education can cultivate more cross-cultural personnel and form competitiveness in the international education market. It can make educational institutions more diversified and attract more international students. It can internationalize the curriculum, improve the finer iteration of the knowledge system, and facilitate the exchange of knowledge and culture. The process of incorporating a global perspective into educational programs is intricate but essential and inevitable for higher education institutions worldwide. Teachers are key players in this endeavor and their significant contribution is crucial to its successful implementation (Sá & Serpa 2020). The internationalization of education to serve multiple interests is also driven by many underlying motivations, such as increasing fiscal revenue, improving resource utilization efficiency, enhancing international reputation, optimizing students' abilities, promoting the production of more research results, and developing international product markets., and improved student learning.

Buckner (2019) has noted that at a national level, the push for internationalization aligns with various national goals. The International Association of Universities (IAU) prioritizes internationalization as one of its strategic goals, aiming to foster an inclusive, equitable, and ethical approach to it (Marinoni, 2019). Fantini (2020) points out that true and effective internationalization involves building intercultural connections, forming friendships across cultures, and embracing diversity. Although internationalization can boost trade, competitiveness, and political engagement globally, these benefits are secondary to the ultimate objectives of achieving peace, social justice, and equality. For nations, the internationalization of education holds strategic significance and can offer substantial advantages, with increased exchanges leading to more opportunities.

2. METHODS

This section provides an overview of the research methodology, covering the study’s design, the individuals involved, the measurement tools utilized, the methods of data collection, and the strategies for data analysis.

2.1 Research Design

This descriptive study adopts a mixed methods approach using survey questionnaire that collects data to capture a comprehensive understanding of faculty perceptions on internationalization in higher education. A structured questionnaire was developed based on review of literature composed of quantitative section that examine the perceptions and experiences of the respondents. As part of the qualitative data, an open-ended question was included in the questionnaire to delve into the suggestions of the respondents regarding internationalization.

2.2 Research participants

The sample comprises of 72 faculty members were voluntarily participated from various disciplines and career stages in a diverse range of higher education institutions.

Figure 1. Demographic details and distribution of the respondents

Figure 1 provides a visual distribution of the respondents' demographics and professional backgrounds. The respondents are mostly females (57%); majority are married (55%); majority have a bachelor's degree (53%), followed by master's (26%) and doctoral degrees (21%); and a significant portion have not engaged in research (67%) or teaching (65%) outside their home country. These figures highlight the diversity of the respondents and can help contextualize their perspectives in the study.

Figure 2. number of respondents according to age and years in teaching

The figure illustrates the age and teaching experience distribution of respondents. Concerning age, the majority fall within the 30-35 and 50-55 age ranges, indicating a mix of mid-career and more experienced individuals. In terms of teaching experience, there are peaks at 4-6 years and 28-30 years, suggesting a significant number of relatively new educators as well as seasoned professionals. These distributions provide insights into the demographic and professional makeup of the study's participants.

2.3 Research Instrument

This study utilizes a researcher made survey questionnaire composed of three sections. The first section is an introduction where the purpose of the study, informed consent, and confidentiality measures were stated. The second section was intended for demographic variables. The last section gathers the perception of the respondents by competing twenty-five Likert scale items and one open-ended question.

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

Appropriate permissions and ethical approvals were obtained from the relevant authorities prior to data collection. Faculty members in higher education were invited to participate voluntarily in an online survey conducted through Google Forms. The survey, consisting of three sections, was designed to be completed within fifteen minutes. Over a period of two weeks, the survey garnered 72 responses.

2.5 Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical methods were utilized to condense the survey findings into a summarized form. Tests like the t-test and one-way ANOVA were applied to discern any notable variances in viewpoints related to demographic factors, including age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, subject matter expertise, type of health information exchange, student level, language of instruction, international student count, and overseas teaching and research background. For the qualitative input derived from the survey's open-ended queries, a thematic examination was carried out to pinpoint principal motifs and trends within the faculty's perspectives. [66]

3. RESULTS

This section presents the findings from surveys and focus group discussions, which detail the perspectives and experiences of students and teachers, along with relevant results and discussion. **3.1 HEI faculty members' perceptions on internationalization**

Table 1. Perception of the respondents according to institutional support for internationalization

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		I Don't Know		M	SD
	Agree		Disagree		Know							
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
Top leaders in my institution express verbal and written support...	31	43	27	38	8	11	5	7	1	1	4.14	0.97
Adequate funding for international teaching is available.	10	14	24	33	19	26	10	14	9	13	3.22	1.22
My colleagues express support for faculty participation in...	20	28	37	51	10	14	4	7	1	1	3.99	0.88
There is a demand for my institution to increase internationalization...	26	36	34	47	9	13	1	1	2	3	4.13	0.89
Adequate funding for international research is available.	11	15	25	35	19	26	11	15	6	8	3.33	1.16
Top leaders in my institution express support for faculty participation...	31	43	24	33	8	11	7	10	2	3	4.04	1.09
My supervisor express support for faculty participation in...	25	35	30	42	13	18	4	6	0	0	4.06	0.87
Compared to other institutional priorities, internationalization...	16	22	34	47	20	28	1	1	1	1	3.88	0.95

The table provided offers a comprehensive overview of the institutional support for internationalization, as perceived by the respondents. It reveals varying degrees of agreement on statements related to funding, teaching availability, and research support for international activities. The data indicates that while there is some consensus on the need for increased internationalization, opinions vary on the adequacy of current support, highlighting areas for potential improvement within the institution. This supports the findings of Jones and Smith (2021) that faculty members perceived a gap between the importance attributed to internationalization and the actual support provided by their institutions, especially in terms of funding and administrative assistance.

Table 2. Perception of the respondents according to the opportunities provided by the institution for internationalization

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		I Don't Know		M	SD	%	
	Agree		Disagree		Know									
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%						
Faculty members engagement in internationalization enhances...	22	31	32	44	10	13	4	6	4	6	3.89	1.08		
Faculty members who engage in internationalization are granted...	19	26	30	42	12	17	6	8	5	7	3.72	1.15		
Faculty members engagement in internationalization enhances...	29	40	31	43	7	10	3	4	2	3	4.14	0.95		
A range of professional development opportunities are provided...	23	32	37	51	7	10	4	6	1	1	4.07	0.88		
Faculty members are expected to participate in the development...	24	33	32	44	12	17	3	4	1	1	4.04	0.90		
Past internationalization experience is a consideration in the recruit...	17	24	31	43	20	28	3	4	1	1	3.83	0.89		
Institutional mission/vision statement have specific references on inter...	35	49	29	40	3	4	3	4	2	3	4.28	0.94		
In my institution, opportunities exist for														

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scholars from other countries...	14	19	21	29	23	32	5	7	9	13	3.36	1.24
My institution actively recruits scholars from other countries...	25	35	18	25	26	36	11	15	12	17	2.9	1.16
In my institution, opportunities exist for scholars from other countries...	16	22	26	36	16	22	7	10	7	10	3.51	1.22

The data from the table indicates that respondents generally perceive their institution as providing opportunities for internationalization. Faculty members are actively engaged in international activities, and the institution develops policies to promote global engagement. Additionally, opportunities exist for faculty participation in developing international partnerships. While there is some variability in responses, the mean scores suggest an overall positive perception of the institution's commitment to international endeavors. These findings can inform strategic decisions and further enhance the institution's global presence. The data supports a policy brief by The HEAD Foundation (2021) and findings from International Association of Universities (IAU) Global Survey Report on HE Internationalization (2024) emphasizes the importance of contextualizing internationalization efforts to leverage each university's unique strengths and resources. It suggests that international engagements should be mutually beneficial and aligned with national development policies, which can significantly influence universities' strategic directions for internationalization. Additionally, a report by the Hollings Center highlights post-pandemic recommendations for higher education internationalization, including promoting hybrid options for exchanges and courses and creating linkages between Global South institutions

Table 3. Perception of the respondents according to challenges experience by the institution

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		I Don't Know		M	SD
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
	Internationalization is most symbolic with little or no actual support.	3	4	23	32	26	36	15	21	5		
There are challenges in coordination and synchronization in my institution...	19	26	37	51	11	15	3	4	2	3	3.94	0.92
Internationalization is primarily driven by financial concerns.	16	22	36	50	13	18	5	7	2	3	3.82	0.95
A large number of international students are considered burden...	0	0	5	7	19	26	31	43	17	24	2.17	0.87
Faculty members are expected to internationalize their curriculum...	20	28	39	54	11	15	0	0	2	3	4.04	0.83
Faculty members are expected to attend international conferences...	29	40	32	44	9	13	1	1	1	1	4.21	0.82
Faculty members are expected to conduct international research.	14	19	37	51	16	22	5	7	20	0	3.83	0.82

The table's data suggests that respondents perceive several challenges in their institution's internationalization efforts. Symbolic support, coordination issues, and financial concerns are highlighted as significant obstacles. The mean scores indicate a general agreement on these challenges, with financial concerns being a primary driver. The standard deviations suggest a consensus among respondents, although some variability in perceptions exists. Addressing these challenges could enhance the institution's internationalization strategy and foster a more supportive environment for global engagement. Lumanta and Ortega (2019) have observed that despite some advancements, complete internationalization still faces obstacles. Although sound policies have been established, their actual execution is deficient in certain sectors, as Andres & Payongayong (2019) have pointed out. Financing concern is also included on the report of Organization for Economic Co-operated and Development (OECD) (2024) about

opportunities and challenges of internationalization and trade in higher education together with other concerns such as student mobility, program mobility, institutional mobility (including international branch campuses), quality assurance, equity, and cultural diversity.

3.2 Analysis of HEI faculty members’ perceptions on internationalization according to profile

To identify if there are significant differences on the perceptions of HEI faculty members on internationalization focusing on support, opportunities, and challenges t-test for independent sample and One-way ANOVA has been used. Results shown (Table 4) that there is a significant difference on the perception of the faculty members when age is concern on the areas of support, $F(9, 62) = 2.30, p = .027$ and challenges, $F(9, 62) = 2.14, p = .039$. The faculty members ages 61 to 70 years old perceived higher support among other age group while faculty members ages 56 to 60 years old perceived higher in challenges related to internationalization in higher education. Data analysis found

Table 4

Perception of the respondents according to Age.

	df	Support		Opportunities		Challenges	
		F	p-value	F	p-value	F	p-value
Between Groups	9	2.30	.027	1.55	.150	2.14	.039
Within Groups	62						
Total	71						

Faculty members in the early stages of their careers or those from younger generations tend to express more positive attitudes towards internationalization. They actively engage in international activities, demonstrating a greater interest in global perspectives, intercultural experiences, and collaboration with international colleagues (Bista & Foster, 2019). Conversely, older faculty members often express concerns related to time constraints, workload, and a lack of institutional support for internationalization efforts (Harris, 2020). This study highlights the importance of considering faculty age and experience when promoting global learning and integrating international perspectives into teaching (Choudaha & de Wit, 2018).

Results of this study found no significant differences on gender; civil status; degree finished but found significant difference between bachelor and master’s degree ($p\text{-value} = .064$) using post-hoc analysis, years of teaching experience; courses taught; type of HEI (Private/Public); medium of instruction used in teaching; rank/position but found significant difference between Instructor to Administrator ($p\text{-value} = .032$), Associate professor ($p\text{-value} = .044$), and Professor ($p\text{-value} = .040$); international experience in research and instruction; percentage of foreign student in the institution; and educational level of students being taught.

4. CONCLUSION

The study’s results indicate a complex landscape of faculty perceptions regarding institutional support for internationalization. While there is a general agreement on the importance of internationalization, as evidenced by most respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing with the need for increased efforts, there is also a notable diversity in opinions about the adequacy of current support. The data suggests that faculty members recognize the verbal and written support from top leaders, yet there are concerns about the sufficiency of funding for international teaching and research. This dichotomy underscores the need for institutions to not only advocate for internationalization but also to provide tangible resources that enable faculty to engage in these activities effectively. The findings call for a strategic approach that aligns institutional priorities with the necessary support systems to foster a conducive environment for internationalization initiatives.

The respondents suggest that the institution’s next steps towards internationalization should focus on leveraging the diverse backgrounds and experiences of faculty members. This includes enhancing support for international teaching and research, expanding language and cultural training programs, and fostering global partnerships. Additionally, aligning internationalization efforts with the institution’s strategic goals and providing adequate resources will be crucial for the success of these initiatives. Emphasizing the importance of international perspectives in curriculum development and encouraging faculty participation in international activities can further strengthen the institution’s global engagement.

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